

Quantitative analysis of inorganic ions in soil employing diffuse reflectance Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (DRS-FTIR)

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Abstract : Nitrogen and sulfur are among the various important macronutrients present in the soil which continuously remain in dynamic equilibrium in the soil-system while participating in essential biogeochemical processes. The levels of ammonium (NH_4^+), nitrate (NO_3^-) and sulphate (SO_4^{2-}) also indicate soil fertility status. The approach of conventional analytical techniques for quantitative determination of inorganic ions restricts their use for large number of samples and *in situ* soil analysis. The objective of this study was to develop a fast and non-destructive method for quantitative determination of inorganic cationic and anionic species, i.e. NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} in soil employing diffuse reflectance Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (DRS-FTIR) with potassium bromide (KBr) matrix as background. The basis of determination of these ions is the selection of non-interfering quantitative vibrational peaks among the various observed peaks for the different symmetry types of the selected multi-atomic ionic units. The peaks at 3132 cm^{-1} (asymmetric stretching vibration, ν_3), 1385 cm^{-1} (asymmetric stretching vibration, ν_3) and 617 cm^{-1} (bending vibration, ν_4) were selected for quantitative determination of NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} respectively, due to the simple reason of strong, sharp signals and avoiding the interfering peaks due to presence of other possible ions in soil. The quantitative analysis has been done by preparing calibration curves by obtaining the peak areas for a wide range of concentration at selected peaks for respective ions. The concentration of NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} were determined, by the present method, to be in the ranges 1.2–5.6, 16.3–23.8 and 11.4–24.3 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ respectively in 8 different mixed featured loam type soil samples collected randomly and freshly from the surrounding areas of the city. The uncertainty in the determination, in terms of rel. std. dev. ($n=10$), were found to be in the range 2.16–4.82, 1.08–3.73 and 1.97–4.12%, respectively for NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} ions. The present method has relatively very high sample throughput as compared to ion-chromatographic (IC) technique. The work proposes a rapid, free of interferences, low cost and non-destructive method employing DRS-FTIR technique for characterization of key components of soil viz. NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} .

Keywords : DRS-FTIR, ammonium, nitrate, sulphate, KBr substrate, soil analysis.

Introduction

Soils are key links in the global carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus and sulphur cycles. These cycles involve soil chemical processes. Some of the processes include decomposition of organic matter, nitrification, denitrification, phosphorus fixation, sulphide oxidation etc.^{1–5}. Thus, soil contains a large number of organic and inorganic components. Ammonium (NH_4^+), nitrate (NO_3^-) and sulphate (SO_4^{2-}) are the major inorganic ions in soil and sediments^{6,7}. These ions follow the important biogeochemical cycles in the environment for the sustainability of ecosystem. Ions such as SO_4^{2-} and NO_3^- are also ma-

ior precursors for acid-rain and soil acidification^{8,9}. Importantly, therefore, estimation of such changing soil ingredients decides the quality and composition of soil, biogeochemical processes in soil and environmental impacts on soils. Hence, quantification of all such ions present in trace amounts in soil is of great concern to know their load, pathway and origin^{10,11}.

For quantitative analysis of inorganic ions in soil there are very good analytical techniques and methods which are available including liquid chromatography¹², chromatography¹³, chemiluminescence (CL) measurements¹⁴, electrochemical¹⁵, spectrofluorimetry¹⁶, capillary electro-

phoresis¹⁷, spectrophotometry¹⁸ and ion chromatography with indirect UV detection method¹⁹. However, some of them are not selective, little sensitive and some need lengthy pretreatment. Invariably, all methods reported above also require more or less a large number of eco-unfriendly chemicals and also the sample throughput is less, as the sample preparation (soil and sediment leaching in water/acidic solution) and analysis requires at least half an hour for one sample. The analysis of these samples via the traditional techniques may take 1 h, with the leaching process taking up to 24 h.

Recently, various infrared techniques have been used widely for the analysis of inorganic species such as ammonium, nitrate and sulphate in soil. Shaviv and his co-workers²⁰ have employed a Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) technique with silver halide fibers for a direct monitoring of soil nitrate. Linker and Weiner²¹ have determined nitrate in soil pastes with improved accuracy through soil identification employing attenuated total reflectance mid-infrared spectroscopy. An alternate method for FTIR determination of soil nitrate using derivative analysis and sample treatments has been developed by Choe and his coworkers²². Roonasi and Holmgren²³ have studied the adsorption behavior surface chemistry of sulphate on magnetite employing attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) technique. Measurement of ammonia emissions from soil manure has been done using gradient FTIR technique²⁴. Diffuse reflectance Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (DRS-FTIR) has been employed for the analysis of added ammonium and nitrate in silica sand and soil by Suwanee and Mark²⁵. The size distribution parameters of the aerosol mass and the associated functional groups were analyzed by infrared spectroscopic technique²⁶. However, most of the above methods describe qualitative identification or semi-quantitative analysis of inorganic ions in soil and aerosols samples. In recent studies^{27,28} DRS-FTIR have been employed for quantitative determination of metaloxy anions at submicrogram level in biological fluids. Therefore, we thought that DRS-FTIR could also serve as an excellent analytical tool for quantitative determination of inorganic species in soil samples for a small sample size, using no reagents and would allow for high sample throughput.

The objectives of this paper are to develop a new,

rapid and precise analytical method for the measurement of submicrogram levels of inorganic ions (viz. NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-}) in soil samples. The objectives also add to the information on the usefulness and application possibilities of non-destructive spectroscopic methods for ambient analysis that today have great advantages compared to many methods reported above. This method is also absolutely free of large amounts of harmful reagents and supports strongly the present day need for environmentally responsible chemistry.

Results and discussion

Qualitative identification of vibrational (infrared) peaks for inorganic ions :

DRS-FTIR provides information about the presence of the inorganic ions without giving any information about associated mono atomic cations like Na^+ , K^+ , etc. The interpretation of observed FTIR spectra was done following the characteristic IR absorption bands for inorganic ions as reported in the available literature²⁹⁻³³. All these characteristics IR absorption bands are checked by standard samples of salt of associated cations. The presence of inorganic ions is commonly related to a strong absorption bands around various peaks (Figs. 1a-c). Table 1 shows the various qualitative infrared absorption bands of inorganic ionic species. Strong peaks at 3132 and at 1405 cm^{-1} of NH_4^+ in the salt for N-H bonds were observed due to the involvement of high asymmetric stretching (ν_3) energy and relatively low bending vibration (ν_4) energy, respectively, in the N-H bonds. Four peaks corresponding to the different modes of N-O bond vibrations were observed at 1385 (very strong), 1050 (weak), 833 (medium but sharp) and 715 and 719 (very weak) cm^{-1} , respectively, due to the following N-O bond energies in the order : asymmetric stretching (ν_3) > symmetric stretching (ν_1) > bending vibration (ν_2) > bending vibration (ν_4). Similarly, three peaks corresponding to the different modes of S-O bond vibrations in Na_2SO_4 were observed at 1117 (strong and broad), 983 (weak and sharp), 617 (strong and sharp) cm^{-1} , respectively, due to the following S-O bond energies in the order : asymmetric stretching (ν_3) > symmetric stretching (ν_1) > bending vibration (ν_4). The reported peak at 415 cm^{-1} for S-O bond, however, was not observed which may possibly be due the low level of salt concentration used.

Fig. 1(a-c). DRS-FTIR spectra of some pure inorganic ions tested for qualitative and quantitative analysis.

Table 1. Infrared absorption bands and different modes of vibration for inorganic ions when used as their salts or compounds

Inorganic ions	Salts/compounds used for DRS-FTIR study	Absorption peak range reported earlier (cm ⁻¹)	Characteristic absorption peaks found in the present work (cm ⁻¹)	Vibrational modes
Ammonium	NH ₄ Cl	3350-3050 1450-1390	3132 (very strong) 1405 (very strong)	Asymmetric stretching (ν ₃) Bending vibrations (ν ₄)
Nitrate	NaNO ₃	1500-1300 1070-1010 850-800 770-715	1385 ^a (very strong) 1050 (weak) 833 (medium, sharp) 715, 719 (very weak)	Asymmetric stretching (ν ₃) Symmetric stretching (ν ₁) Bending vibrations (ν ₂) Bending vibrations (ν ₄)
Sulphate	Na ₂ SO ₄	1134-1087 1076-965 618 451	1117 (strong and broad) 983 (weak and sharp) 617 ^a (strong and sharp)	Asymmetric stretching (ν ₃) Symmetric stretching (ν ₁) Bending vibrations (ν ₄) Bending vibrations (ν ₂)

These values are very close to the values reported in the literature and any minor differences, if at all, may be attributed to the technical advancement in the instrumentation. For the observation of all qualitative spectral peaks due to ions, two-point baseline corrections were performed over the same spectral range for all analytes/samples.

Analytical infrared peak selection for quantitative determination of inorganic ions :

The quantitative determinations were based on the selection of a quantitative analytical peak among all observed vibrational peaks for each inorganic ion obtained by DRS-FTIR. Table 1 shows the peak selected for the

quantitative determination of each inorganic ion. This analytical infrared peak selected for the quantitative determination of inorganic ions were based on the criterion viz. strongest (sharp and intense), without shoulder, no diffusion or merger, non-interfering (sample profile) and quantitative behavior. Each ionic species gave at least 3–4 vibrational peaks at the selected concentration ranges but only one or two peaks showed consistency. Some peaks were shifted or disappeared with the lower analyte concentration. The peak at 3132 cm^{-1} (asymmetric stretching vibration, ν_3) has been selected among the two distinctively observed peaks at 3132 and 1405 cm^{-1} for the quantitative determination of NH_4^+ ion. The peak at 1385 cm^{-1} (asymmetric stretching vibration, ν_3) has been selected among the four observed signals at 1385, 1050, 833, 719 cm^{-1} for the quantitative determination of NO_3^- and the peak at 617 cm^{-1} (bending vibration, ν_4) has been selected among the three observed peaks at 617, 983 and 1117 cm^{-1} for SO_4^{2-} determination due to the simple reason of strong, sharp signals and avoiding the interfering peaks due to presence of other possible ions in soil.

Analytical and statistical parameters :

Instrumental analytical parameters such as the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ), and the statistical parameters for precision analysis such as standard deviation (SD) and relative standard deviation (RSD) values for NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} were also calculated. The LOD³⁴, defined as the concentration at which we can decide whether an element is present or not that is, the point where we can just distinguish a signal from the background concentration of the analyte, or the amount of analyte causing more absorbance than thrice the standard deviation value for 10 replicate measurements of absorbance for blank at 90% confidence limit, of the present method is. The quantitation is generally agreed to begin at a concentration equal to 10 standard deviations of the blank, called as the LOQ³⁴, which is numerically 3.3 times that of the LOD. The LOD of the method was calculated to be 0.08 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ NH_4^+ , 0.05 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ NO_3^- and 0.1 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ SO_4^{2-} . The LOQ value was calculated to be 0.20 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ NH_4^+ , 0.07 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ NO_3^- and 0.25 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ SO_4^{2-} . The precision and uncertainty in the analysis by the present method in terms of SD and RSD ($n = 10$) at a test level 5 $\mu\text{g 20 } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ solution for each ions were found

to be ± 0.04 and 1.82; ± 0.03 and 1.95; ± 0.07 $\mu\text{g 20 } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ and 1.73% respectively for NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} .

Statistical data fit for calibration curves :

The correlation coefficients, intercept, slope and other statistical parameters such as degree of freedom adjusted coefficient of determination (DF Adj r^2), fit standard error (Fit Std Err) and F-statistics (F-stat) as obtained for 2 sets of X-Y data for the quantification of ammonium, nitrate and sulphate ions using the software Table Curve 2D are also shown in Table 2. The software, Table Curve 2D, utilizes four common goodness of fit statistics.

The correlation co-efficient ' r ' values for full range of concentrations of NH_4^+ and NO_3^- ions were found to be relatively lower ($\text{NH}_4^+ - 0.886$, $\text{NO}_3^- - 0.874$) than the small concentration ranges of these ions (0.982–0.996, NH_4^+ ; 0.993–0.999, NO_3^-). The coefficients of determination (CD r^2) values were much closer to 1.0 for small concentration ranges of NH_4^+ (0.964–0.993) and NO_3^- (0.988–0.999) than for the full range concentrations of these ions. The fit standard error (Fit Std Err) values, again, approach towards zero for small concentration ranges of above ions (0.025–0.110, NH_4^+ ; 0.015–0.123, NO_3^-). Similarly, the F-statistics (F-stat) values for smaller range of concentrations were remarkably higher (135–718, NH_4^+ ; 417–7653, NO_3^-) than that for the full range concentration of these ions. This indicates that with increase in concentration folds the data scatter from the linearity also increases. However, the ' r ', 'CD r^2 ', 'Fit Std Err' and 'F-stat' values for both full and small concentration ranges of SO_4^{2-} were found to be 0.993, 0.988, 0.250, 1349; and 0.995–0.998, 0.992–0.998, 0.0086–0.2286, 806–2471, respectively. As a straight line fit turns out to be more ideal, the r^2 value approaches 1.0 (0 represent a complete lack of fit), the standard error decreases toward zero, and the F-statistic reaches toward infinity. Thus, the data obtained verifies the ideal rank of the calibration curves. However, for more precise analysis small concentration ranges could be employed for NH_4^+ and NO_3^- determination whereas SO_4^{2-} could be determined at any defined concentration range.

Inter-ionic effects :

Inter-ionic effects were tested at different concentration levels of ions per 0.1 g KBr. To the test solution varied amount of the foreign species were added and the

Table 2. Analysis of inorganic ions by DRS-FTIR technique in soil samples

Inorganic ions	Amount of ions ⁻ found					F value ^d (sd_1^2/sd_2^2 , $sd_1 > sd_2$)	t value ^e $\pm t = \frac{\sqrt{N}}{s}(\bar{X} - \mu)$
	Present method (DRS-FTIR)			Standard method (IC) ^a			
	Concentration ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	Rel. std. dev. ($n = 10$) (%)	DRS-FTIR/IC mean rel. discrepancies ^b (%)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	Rel. std. dev. ($n = 4$) (%)		
Ammonium^c							
1.	5.59	2.67	5.1	5.54	1.33	4.04	1.061
2.	2.10	2.70	-2.9	2.13	1.98	1.80	1.673
3.	1.83	4.55	3.6	1.79	4.45	1.09	1.523
4.	1.25	2.16	-1.3	1.26	1.75	1.75	1.152
5.	3.33	2.66	3.1	3.30	2.43	1.16	1.060
6.	4.32	3.52	4.3	4.28	3.34	1.15	0.832
7.	2.32	2.94	3.9	2.28	2.64	1.33	1.860
8.	4.63	4.82	-7.2	4.70	4.73	1.01	0.976
Nitrate^c							
1.	23.76	2.49	-8.1	23.84	1.43	3.02	0.327
2.	20.76	3.73	-9.0	20.85	1.98	3.53	0.367
3.	16.54	1.08	4.6	16.49	2.23	4.22	0.883
4.	18.43	2.33	-5.3	18.48	2.64	1.29	0.442
5.	17.64	2.65	5.9	17.58	2.39	1.24	0.406
6.	19.45	2.93	-3.3	19.48	1.34	4.78	0.166
7.	16.32	1.98	6.5	16.26	2.63	1.76	0.587
8.	21.45	1.88	-5.1	21.50	1.55	1.47	0.392
Sulphate^c							
1.	24.33	2.24	-5.7	24.39	1.07	3.83	0.348
2.	16.07	4.12	-6.2	16.13	4.15	1.02	0.286
3.	12.92	1.97	6.7	12.85	1.20	2.78	0.871
4.	21.27	3.76	5.9	21.21	3.05	1.52	0.237
5.	16.39	2.16	5.8	16.33	2.36	2.39	0.535
6.	15.34	3.29	-4.2	15.38	2.10	2.44	0.250
7.	11.42	2.51	4.9	11.37	2.32	1.18	1.928
8.	19.83	2.06	-5.2	19.88	2.43	1.40	0.387

^aIon chromatographic method.^bError calculated with respect to the values obtained by the standard method.^cAmount of tested ions found in 8 different mixed featured loam type soil samples collected freshly from the surrounding areas of the city.^dTabulated F-values at 95% confidence level are as follows : for $N_1 = 10$, $N_2 = 4$ (or $\nu_1 = 9$, $\nu_2 = 3$), 8.81.^eTabulated t-values at 95% confidence level are as follows : for $N_1 = 10$ (i.e. for $\nu_1 = N_1 - 1$, 9 degrees of freedom), 2.262.

sample was then analyzed as described in the present method. The band position and spectral intensity of tested ions remained intact even in the presence of 50–200 fold molar excess of the following tested multi-atomic cationic and anionic species including CN^- , OH^- , SCN^- , ClO_2^- , ClO_3^- , ClO_4^- , BrO_3^- , IO_3^- , IO_4^- ,

HCO_3^- , MnO_4^- , SeO_3^{2-} , AsO_3^{2-} , FeO_4^{2-} , SiO_4^{2-} , BO_3^{3-} , AsO_4^{3-} , formate, acetate, oxalate, succinate, cinnamate and citrate. NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} do not interfere in the determination of each other at the selected wave-number values. Mono-atomic cations and anions like Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , F^- , etc. have absolutely

no adverse effect in the quantitative determination of nitrate since they do not possess dipole change, therefore their effect is seen only below 200 cm^{-1} with large number of unresolvable spectral lines with poor sensitivities.

Sample throughput :

Once the sample is made ready for the analysis it takes only a few minutes to analyse for one process. After the calibration curve is plotted, one sample could be analyzed within only three minutes – two minutes for filling up the sample in sample holder, sample handling and cleaning, and 45 s for FTIR scanning of the sample in the range 200 to 4000 cm^{-1} for 45 scans. Thus, as many as 20 samples could be analyzed in an hour by using DRS-FTIR method. Even more time could be saved if the number of scans and scan range were reduced. DRS-FTIR combined with the prediction from calibration curves is thus genuinely a time saving technique, additionally, being a non-destructive method; the analyzed samples could be preserved for further or advanced investigation.

Experimental

Determination of inorganic ions in soil samples :

The dried soils, sampled and prepared as outlined below, were taken directly with the help of spatula and the sample holder was filled completely. Amount of sample introduced for analysis was obtained by subtracting the pre and post weighed values of the sample holder before and after filling the samples. The samples were scanned and absorption was measured at 3132, 1385 and 617 cm^{-1} for ammonium, nitrate and sulphate, respectively. Thus, from the spectra of the neat soil samples, equivalent peak heights/area were measured, and from these the predictions of the inorganic ions were made using the cali-

bration curve derived from the spectra (peak areas and the related calibration curve) of each ionic species which were added to the KBr samples in concentration ranges, prior to drying and scanning. Fig. 2 shows the Kubelka Munk spectrum, of a real and neat soil sample, covering a wide frequency range for qualitative identification of spectral peaks of ammonium, nitrate and sulphate.

The relative standard deviation, for a set of eight determinations in each case, was shown in Table 2. The DRS-FTIR/IC mean relative discrepancies which give a measure of the mean relative error in the analysis of selected ions by the present method were found to be in the range -7.2 to -1.3%, -9.0 to -3.3% and 6.7 to -4.2%, respectively for ammonium, nitrate and sulphate. Thus, the results of the present method were compared to that of the ion-chromatographic method³⁵ and the data were in close agreement (Table 2).

All the results were compared with the results obtained by the reference method statistically. It was shown that the difference between the results were insignificant (Table 2). Different samples were analyzed for the determination of ammonium, nitrate and sulphate by the proposed method for the purpose of analytical quality assurance (AQA) test. A high degree of correlation was observed between the results obtained by the proposed method and the standard method.

The F-test was performed at 95% probability to compare the result of the present method with that of the standard method. Because in all cases the calculated values of F ($\text{sd}_1^2/\text{sd}_2^2$) (1.01-4.04, NH_4^+ ; 1.24-4.78 NO_3^- ; 1.02-3.83, SO_4^{2-}) were less than the tabulated F value (8.81) at the 95% confidence level, the difference between the results of the present method and that of the standard method were not significant. The t-test was performed at 95% confidence level. Again in all the cases

Fig. 2. Kubelka Munk spectrum of a real and neat soil sample.

the calculated *t*-values (0.832–1.860, NH_4^+ ; 0.166–0.883 NO_3^- ; 0.237–1.928, SO_4^{2-}) were less than the tabulated value of *t* (2.262), indicating no statistical difference between the results obtained by the present method and the standard method.

Sampling and sample preparation :

Soil samples were collected from representative areas in and around the city. Surface soil was mixed thoroughly with soil from a depth of 60–90 cm to get a complete homogeneous sample. The samples (~0.1 g) were crushed to fine particles by grinding for 2–5 min in an agate mortar. After sieving through 200 mesh size sieves, the samples were dried in an electric oven at 40 °C for not more than 10 min as prolonged heating might reduce the actual content of the analyte.

Apparatus :

Fourier-transform infrared spectra were recorded with a FTIR 8400S (Shimadzu Corporation Analytical and Measuring Instruments Division, Kyoto, Japan) using diffuse reflectance accessory (DRS-FTIR). The spectrometer was equipped with an L-alanine doped Deuterated Triglycine Sulphate (DTGS) detector. The optimum conditions set for DRS-FTIR analysis of the samples were as follows : sample volume – about 15 milligram, sample form – ground soil (200 mesh), apodization function – Happ-Ganzel, resolution – 4 cm^{-1} , number of scans – 45, time of scan – auto, reference blank – finely ground KBr, measurement mode – reflectance in Kubelka Munk unit, beam – internal, mirror speed – 2.8 mm s^{-1} . The spectral range used for identification of peaks of ammonium, nitrate and sulphate ions were 3600–1200, 1600–600, 1300–500 cm^{-1} , respectively. The baseline correction range for quantitative analysis of all the above ions were 3500–2700, 1500–1250, 650–550 cm^{-1} , respectively.

Sartorius electronic balance (AG, Göttingen, Germany) model CP225D (precision 10 μg) was used for measurement of weight difference prior and after the soil sampling. Calibrated glass apparatus were used for volumetric measurements. Because of the high sensitivity of the method, special care was taken during handling of all glasswares to avoid contamination. Glassware were cleaned with hot chromic acid and after proper washing, rinsed with ultrapure water. Millipore ultra purifier system was used to obtain pure distilled water.

Reagents and standard solutions :

At every stage of experiment, special precautions were taken to avoid contamination from reagents and glass

apparatus. Chemicals (potassium bromide, ammonium nitrate, ammonium sulphate, ammonium chloride, ammonium carbonate) used in this analysis are of infrared spectrometric grade (Merck, KGaA 64271, Darmstadt, Germany).

Standard stock solutions of 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ were prepared dissolving suitable amount of salts of ions. Appropriate dilutions were made to obtain solutions containing ion concentrations in the range 0.05–100 $\mu\text{g 20 } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$.

Development of calibration curves :

A series of exactly weighed (100 mg) and finely ground potassium bromide (KBr) were taken in small test tubes (10 mm outer diameter \times 45 mm length, without annular rims). To these using micropipette tips, varied known concentrations of inorganic ions in the range 0.15–2.5, 2.5–35, 15–50 $\mu\text{g 20 } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ (NH_4^+), 0.05–1.5, 1.5–25, 25–50 $\mu\text{g 20 } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ (NO_3^-) and 0.25–3.5, 2.5–15.5, 5.5–100 $\mu\text{g 20 } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ (SO_4^{2-}) were spiked. Then all the standard KBr-matrices were dried in a water-bath at 40 °C for 7 min. After drying KBr-matrix were thoroughly mixed. These dried standards were analyzed by the DRS-FTIR.

The Kubelka Munk (KM) conversion uses the formula below to invert a reflectance spectrum measured by the diffuse reflection method into a quantitative spectrum that correlates with the concentration of the sample.

$$f(R) = \frac{(1 - R)^2}{2R} = \frac{k}{s}$$

where *k* = molecular extinction coefficient; *s* = scattering coefficient; *R* = reflectance (power spectrum of sample/power spectrum of dilution material, KBr in the present case).

With the help of KM conversion all spectra of the standards as well as samples are baseline-corrected before the quantitative analysis of the samples could be performed for a specific peak in the spectrum.

Thus, the calibration curves for peak area was prepared by utilizing the respective Kubelka Munk spectrum obtained for the equivalent amount of inorganic ions. The software IR Solution (© 2002, Creon-Laboratory-Control, AG, Shimadzu) converts automatically the reflectance spectrum into the KM spectrum for smoothing the baseline (Fig. 1). The calibration curve was obtained by plotting full range concentrations of standards versus the absorbance. The minimum and maximum concentration range

Table 3. Statistical data for the different calibration curves prepared for low, moderate and high concentrations of ammonium, nitrate and sulphate ions

Calibration curve (CCn)	Concentration range ^a	Intercept (a)	Slope (b)	St. line equation [#] (y = a + bx)	Correlation coefficient (r)	CD r ²	DF	Fit Std Err	F-stat	RSD (n = 8)
CCn-NH-1	0.15-50	0.573	1.547	$\log C NH_4^+ = 0.65 A_{peak} - 0.37$	0.886	0.785	0.752	0.778	51.1	2.2
CCn-NH-2	0.15-2.5	0.032	0.126	$C NH_4^+ = 7.94 A_{peak} - 0.25$	0.982	0.964	0.946	0.025	135.7	1.9
CCn-NH-3	2.5-35	0.220	0.088	$C NH_4^+ = 11.36 A_{peak} - 2.55$	0.996	0.993	0.989	0.097	718.2	2.1
CCn-NH-4	15-50	0.357	0.083	$C NH_4^+ = 12.05 A_{peak} - 4.30$	0.995	0.991	0.987	0.110	593.1	1.9
CCn-NO-1	0.05-50	0.982	1.699	$\log C NO_3^- = 0.59 A_{peak} - 0.58$	0.874	0.764	0.732	0.991	51.7	2.1
CCn-NO-2	0.05-1.5	0.030	0.227	$C NO_3^- = 4.45 A_{peak} - 0.13$	0.993	0.988	0.982	0.015	427.2	2.1
CCn-NO-3	1.5-25	0.295	0.113	$C NO_3^- = 8.85 A_{peak} - 2.61$	0.993	0.988	0.982	0.123	417.4	2.2
CCn-NO-4	25-50	0.358	0.107	$C NO_3^- = 9.35 A_{peak} - 3.61$	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.032	7653.4	1.9
CCn-SO-1	0.25-100	0.358	0.074	$\log C SO_4^{2-} = 1.30 A_{peak} - 0.68$	0.993	0.988	0.986	0.250	1349.4	2.1
CCn-SO-2	0.25-3.5	0.135	0.110	$C SO_4^{2-} = 9.09 A_{peak} - 1.22$	0.997	0.996	0.995	0.0086	1627.9	1.7
CCn-SO-3	2.5-15.5	0.164	0.108	$C SO_4^{2-} = 9.26 A_{peak} - 1.51$	0.998	0.998	0.996	0.0265	2471.6	2.2
CCn-SO-4	5.5-100	0.740	0.068	$C SO_4^{2-} = 14.7 A_{peak} - 108.8$	0.995	0.992	0.989	0.2286	806.3	2.8

NH-1 - Data for logarithmic plot of ammonium concentration (full range) vs peak area.
 NH-(2-4) - Data for plot of ammonium concentration vs peak area.
 NO-1 - Data for logarithmic plot of nitrate concentration (full range) vs peak area.
 NO-(2-4) - Data for plot of nitrate concentration vs peak area.
 SO-1 - Data for logarithmic plot of sulphate concentration (full range) vs peak area.
 SO-(2-4) - Data for plot of sulphate concentration vs peak area.

^aConcentration range. $\mu g NH_4^+ / NO_3^- / SO_4^{2-} / 20 \mu L$ aqueous solution spiked in 0.1 g KBr.
[#]Data processed by the software Table Curve 2D v5.01.01.
^gConcentration of inorganic ions - $\mu g / 20 \mu L$ aqueous solution spiked in 0.1 g KBr. A_{peak} = Area under the peak.
 In the following descriptions, SSM = sum of squares about the mean, SSE = sum of squared errors (residuals), n = total number of data values and m = number of coefficients in the model. 'DF', the degree of freedom = 'n - m'. Coefficient of Determination (CD, r-squared), r² = 1 - SSE/SSM; Degree of Freedom Adjusted Coefficient of Determination, DF Adj r² = (1 - SSE*(n - 1))/(SSM*(DF - 1)); Fit Standard Error (Root Mean Square Error), Std Err = sqrt(SSE/DF); F-statistic, F-stat = ((SSM - SSE)/(n - 1))/(SSE/DF).

for each inorganic ions which were observed in the data, was in the ratio 1 : 200 (Table 3). The linear curves, apparently prepared with linear regression analysis, were used. The software Table Curve 2D v5.01.01 (Systat Software Inc.) was used for processing the obtained data which employed a linear calibration model with equation $y = a + bx$ for all ions.

The applicability of DRS-FTIR technique has been demonstrated by the quantitative determination of the multi-atomic inorganic ions in soil samples. Highly satisfactory results were obtained. The proposed method is extremely rapid because once calibration curves are prepared spectral information regarding absorbance and peak area values may be obtained within 3 min. Thus, the method has a high sample throughput value. Use of tremendously reduced sample size is the advantage of this method. Reagentless analysis and low detection limit value also adds up to the beauty of this method which also supports the need of Green Chemistry research. However, it may be worth mentioning that some of validation using the traditional laboratory techniques may still be necessary to confirm the predicted values.

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